

Preliminary Design of a Steam-Cooled Reactor Using LEU+ Fuel

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ABSTRACT

This research proposes a Steam-Cooled Small Modular Reactor (SCSMR) design and performs a neutronic study. The SCSMR utilizes Low Enriched Uranium (LEU+) fuel with an enrichment of 10 wt% and is designed for a thermal power output of 30 MWth. The core configuration consists of 21 fuel assemblies (Westinghouse 17×17 type) with an active length and diameter of 280 cm, achieving approximately 30-year lifetime without refueling. All neutronic analyses were conducted using the Monte Carlo code MCNP6.3 with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library. The design applies the optimum-moderation condition to the reactor core, where reactivity is primarily controlled by adjusting the steam density and the inter-assembly gap. The results indicate that the system reaches a critical state at a steam density of $0.32 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ with an inter-assembly gap of 12 cm. The neutron spectrum of the SCSMR is identified as an intermediate spectrum, predominantly in the epithermal energy range. Furthermore, the study confirms that sufficient shutdown margin and reactivity control can be maintained through the proposed steam density and gap adjustment strategies. This preliminary evaluation demonstrates the feasibility of the SCSMR as an innovative long-cycle reactor concept, with further studies required for coupled thermal-hydraulic validation and structural optimization.

Keywords: Steam-cooled reactor, MCNP, LEU+

1. INTRODUCTION

Typical fresh PWR fuel assemblies are stored in a dry New Fuel Storage Vault (NFSV) before being moved to the core for operation. During emergency such as firefighting activities in an NFSV, the introduction of low-density hydrogenous media, such as foam or mist, can create an accidental moderation environment.[1] Research indicates that these conditions can trigger an optimum moderation peak, where maximum reactivity occurs at a water moderator density of approximately $0.1\text{--}0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. [2] This phenomenon, resulting from an increased resonance escape probability and fast fission factor within the assembly gaps, can set the limiting condition for criticality safety in storage facilities.

Inspired by this physical phenomenon, this study explores a new reactor design that intentionally applies the optimum moderation condition to an operating core. While traditional light water reactor (LWR) are designed to be over-moderated at high water densities, This study proposes a Steam-Cooled Small Modular Reactor (SCSMR) that utilizes Low Enriched Uranium (LEU+) fuel to achieve high performance under these low-density conditions.

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The SCSMR offers distinct advantages compared to existing advanced reactor concepts. Unlike the Boiling Water Reactor (BWR), which operates in a two-phase saturation regime and requires complex components like steam separators and recirculation pumps, the SCSMR utilizes heated steam as a single-phase coolant at subcritical pressure. This design significantly simplifies the system, removing the need for moisture separators, dryers, and steam generators, thereby reducing the overall balance-of-plant (BOP) mass. Furthermore, while SuperCritical Water-cooled Reactor (SCWR) target high efficiency above the critical point (374°C, 22.1 MPa), they face severe challenges in materials and thermal-hydraulics. The SCSMR operates at reduced pressure, allowing for thinner vessel and piping requirements compared to SCWRs.[3-5]

The primary uniqueness of the SCSMR lies in its reactivity control strategy. By adjusting the steam density and the inter-assembly gap, the reactor can be tuned to operate near the optimum moderation peak, enabling high reactivity and flexible power adjustment. This approach allows for a simplified control mechanism and enhanced neutronic efficiency.

2. ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

2.1. Analysis Code

In this study, the MCNP6.3 code, developed by Los Alamos National Laboratory, was used for particle transport simulations based on the Monte Carlo method.[6] To ensure high accuracy and minimize errors associated with group condensation, the continuous-energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VIII.0 was utilized.[7] All eigenvalue calculations were performed with 10,000 neutron histories per cycle for a total of 5,000 cycles, skipping the first 50 cycles to ensure statistical convergence and stability. Under these simulation parameters, the statistical uncertainty of the calculated k_{eff} values was maintained within 12 pcm to ensure the high reliability of the neutronic results.

2.2. Maximum Reactivity Condition

As water density in the system decreases from 1 g·cm⁻³, the mean free path (MFP) of neutrons increases due to fewer collisions with hydrogen. This reduces the thermal neutron flux reaching the fuel, causing the U235 thermal fission rate to decline, which typically results in an initial k_{eff} decrease within the 0.6 to 1 g·cm⁻³ range. The temperature of system is assumed to be 293K. However, at lower densities (approximately 0.2 to 0.6 g·cm⁻³), two counteracting effects become dominant: Thermal neutron absorption by the decreasing absolute volume of water is mitigated, and neutron spectrum shift toward higher energies enhances the contribution of fuel fast-range reactions, particularly U238 fast fission. When these beneficial effects collectively compensate for the initial thermalization loss, the system reaches the condition of optimum moderation, where k_{eff} peaks. Subsequently, in the lowest density region (0.1 to 0.2 g·cm⁻³), moderation becomes severely insufficient, causing the neutron spectrum to be excessively hardened, which results in a rapid drop in the thermal fission rate and an accompanying sharp decline in k_{eff} . [8]

Figure 1. k_{eff} behavior for NFSV according to changes in water density.

2.3. Core Configuration

Figure 2. SCSMR Design overview

The proposed SCSMR is designed with a thermal power of 30 MWth and utilizes a reactivity control strategy based on the adjustment of steam density and inter-assembly gaps. The core design overview is illustrated in Figure 2. The core consists of 21 fuel assemblies arranged to optimize the moderation effect within the epithermal-dominant spectrum. Each fuel assembly adopts a Westinghouse 17x17 configuration, containing 264 fuel rods and 25 guide tubes. Within each guide tube, reactivity control devices are inserted to manage the core's operational reactivity.

The fuel rods are composed of LEU+ pellets with 10 wt% enrichment UO_2 encapsulated in Zircaloy-4 cladding, which, along with Zircaloy-4 guide tubes, minimizes parasitic neutron absorption. The active fuel length and the overall core diameter are both specified as 280 cm. Regarding the thermal-hydraulic design, the reactor operates with a core inlet temperature of approximately 500K and an outlet temperature range of 750K. These parameters are selected to ensure stable coolant behavior while

providing sufficient safety margins against heat transfer deterioration and excessive fuel temperature rise. The key design specifications are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Design specifications of SCSMR

Items	Material	Dimension
Fuel	UO ₂ (10wt%)	D: 0.784cm H: 280cm
Cladding & Guide tube	Zircaloy-4	ID: 0.8cm OD: 0.8898cm
Vessel	SS304	Thickness: 10cm
Moderator & coolant	Steam	Density: 0.1~1 g·cm ⁻³
Full core		D: 280cm H: 280cm

3. RESULT ANALYSIS

3.1. Gap-Dependent Reactivity Change

Figure 3. k_{eff} behavior according to changes in steam density and inter-assembly gap

Figure 3 compares the k_{eff} behavior as a function of steam density for three different inter-assembly gaps. To simulate reactor operating conditions, the calculations were performed assuming a fuel temperature of 1000 K and a coolant temperature of 750 K. The curves were obtained by initially calculating the steam density from 0.10 to 1.00 g·cm⁻³ in 0.10 g·cm⁻³ steps, with subsequent refinement near the reactivity peak using 0.02 g·cm⁻³ steps to ensure precision. In this study, the gap represents the distance between adjacent fuel assemblies. As the gap increases, the external slowing-down region forms a wider flux trap. Furthermore, as the steam density decreases, the neutron mean free path increases, enhancing

the probability of neutrons reaching adjacent assemblies and leading to the optimum-moderation phenomenon in the low-density region.

A steep gradient in reactivity is observed around the peak, which suggests that the reactor power can be flexibly adjusted by controlling the steam density to adjust excessive initial reactivity and external demand. Considering design constraints for an adequate coolant flow area and the mechanical requirements for reactivity control devices within the inter-assembly spaces, a 12 cm gap was selected as the minimum distance and adopted for the core concept. All results presented in this analysis maintained a statistical uncertainty within 11 pcm, ensuring the reliability of the observed reactivity trends.

3.2. Fission spectrum

Figure 4. normalized neutron spectrum as a function of water density (gap=12cm)

Figure 4 illustrates the neutron spectra at a 12 cm inter-assembly gap for various moderator densities ranging from 0.20 to 1.00 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. The spectra were obtained using the F4 tally with user-defined energy bins. In this study, the energy ranges are categorized as thermal (0.025 eV to 1 eV), epithermal (1 eV to 1 keV), and fast (1 keV to 10 MeV). The y-axis of the graph represents the normalized neutron flux per neutron.

As the moderator density increases, the number of hydrogen collisions per unit volume rises, which enhances the moderation and results in a more thermalized spectrum. Conversely, as the density decreases, fission neutrons experience fewer collisions, causing the spectrum to harden. At the optimum moderation density of 0.32 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, the thermal peak is significantly depressed, and the spectrum shifts toward higher energy levels. This indicates that the proposed SCSMR core operates within an epithermal-dominated spectrum.

3.3. Control margin & Reactivity temperature coefficient

Figure 5. core layout with inserted B_4C control rods

To ensure reactor safety, sufficient shutdown margin must be maintained by inserting adequate negative reactivity during an emergency. The SCSMR core utilizes control rods inserted through guide tubes within the fuel assembly, employing B_4C enriched with B-10 up to 90 wt%. Our analysis confirms that these control rods possess sufficient control worth to manage the initial high reactivity, complemented by the reactivity feedback from changes in steam density.

Table 2 compares the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} between normal operation and the All Rods In (ARI) state. The results demonstrate that the control rods alone provide an adequate shutdown margin and ensure sufficient subcriticality. Specifically, in a postulated accident scenario where the core is flooded with cold boron water (2000 ppm), the k_{eff} was calculated to be 0.5411. The reason for the lower k_{eff} in this cold shutdown state is that the increased density of the cold coolant enhances neutron moderation. However, the high concentration of Boron-10 has an exceptionally large absorption cross-section in the resulting thermal energy spectrum, leading to a significant reduction in reactivity.

Furthermore, the Fuel Temperature Coefficient (FTC) and Coolant Temperature Coefficient (CTC) were calculated to evaluate the inherent safety of the core, as presented in Table 3. With nominal temperatures set at 1000 K for the fuel and 750 K for the coolant, we assumed fluctuations of 100 K and 50 K, respectively, for the calculations. The results confirm that both coefficients remain negative, ensuring inherent safety through self-regulating feedback mechanisms that suppress power increases.

Table II. k_{eff} under normal and shutdown condition

condition	k_{eff}
ARO	1.2951
ARI	0.91172
Cold shutdown	0.5411

STD \pm 12pcm

Table III. k_{eff} under normal and shutdown condition

Parameters		Value* [pcm/K]
FTC	900K-1000K	-1.501
	1000K-1100K	-2.026
CTC	700K-750K	-0.191
	750K-800K	-0.166

$$\alpha_T = (\rho_2 - \rho_1)/(T_2 - T_1) = ((1 - 1/k_{eff,2}) - (1 - 1/k_{eff,1}))/ (T_2 - T_1)$$

3.4. Depletion calculation

Figure 6. Result of Depletion calculation

To evaluate the operational lifetime and depletion characteristics of the SCSMR core, we performed an analysis with a rated thermal power of 30 MWth as a key design parameter. Burnup calculations were conducted using the BURN card in MCNP6, coupled with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross-section library. To ensure consistency in the calculations, no boron was included in the core. The steam density was maintained at a constant 0.32 g/cm³, which corresponds to the point of maximum reactivity, while the fuel and coolant temperatures were fixed at 1000 K and 750 K, respectively. Furthermore, a single-batch fuel cycle was assumed, with no intermediate refueling or reshuffling during the entire operation.

Figure 6 illustrates the evolution of the effective multiplication factor as a function of operating time. As burnup proceeds, k_{eff} exhibits an approximately linear decrease. Based on this trend, it was confirmed that the core can sustain continuous operation for approximately 30 years without the need for additional fuel replacement.

The high excess reactivity occurring at the beginning of cycle (BOC) can be sufficiently controlled through a combination of control rods inserted into the guide tubes and negative feedback from steam density variations. In particular, the designed control rod worth is sufficient to offset the initial excess reactivity. The results demonstrate that precise reactivity control and burnup compensation can be achieved by adjusting the steam density during operation.

4. CONCLUSION

This study proposes a new steam cooled small modular reactor (SCSMR) concept that leverages the steam based optimum moderation in the existing fuel storage rack (NFSV) safety analysis. The 30MWt SCSMR employs typical PWR fuel assembly but LEU+ fuel and wide arrangement of fuel assembly with lowering steam density. Neutronic analyses have been performed using MCNP6.3 and various sensitive calculations including depletion analysis are also carried out. From the results, an optimal SCSMR is proposed with a 12 cm inter assembly gap and steam density of $0.32 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ with a proper temperature and pressure. The thermal analysis is remained as a future work for controlling steam density with various temperature and pressure conditions. The neutron spectrum of SCSM is hardened with decreasing density. And control plates between fuel assembly gap are proposed to ensure shutdown. The core can sustain a continuous operating cycle length of around 30 years.

As a future work, the thorium based fuel cycle may be applied for intermediate reactor of SCSMR by providing breeding effect. And steep reactivity gradient near the optimum peak requires precise steam density adjustment. Thus additional mechanism of controlling steam density is to be developed. And thermal-hydraulic analysis is required to define stable region of lower density with a proper temperature and pressure. However this study is expected to contribute to develop new innovative nuclear reactor concept.

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